

ISic0757

I.Sicily inscription 0757

Language

Latin

Type

funerary (?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Assorus

Place of origin (modern)

Assoro

Provenance

Contrada Morra/Murra

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 653659

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 186 no.70.2

Morel, J.-P. 1963. Recherches archéologiques et topographiques dans la région d'Assoro (province d'Enna, Sicile). *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité*. 75: 263-301. At 286-287 no.20 fig.24

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